

DETERMINANTS OF INTERNET-BASED TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS IN NIGERIAN INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS

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ABSTRACT

The adoption of Internet-based Technological Innovations (IBTI) by firms within industrial clusters has been reported to enhance technological and economic gains especially in the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) era. Using appropriate standard methods, this study investigates the determinants of the adoption of IBTI among 343 firms in Nigerian industrial clusters. The result revealed that the determinants such as the performance expectancy ($\beta = 0.392$), effort expectancy ($\beta = 0.607$) and price value ($\beta = 0.266$) were positive and relevant in influencing the adoption of IBTI, while other drivers such as the attitude toward using the technology ($\beta = -0.109$), service provider's credibility ($\beta = -0.039$), facilitating conditions ($\beta = -0.106$) and economic flexibility ($\beta = -0.078$) were negative, but also significantly determine the adoption of IBTI by the industrial firms. Thus, the availability of technological infrastructure to support industrial firms' performance and attitudes toward using these innovations are most critical, while the proper utilization of the innovation requires understanding the impacts of cluster patterns and dynamics.

Keywords: Adoption, Internet of things, IBTI, Industrial clusters, Development, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

The role of technological innovations in sustainable development presents important considerations for industrial policy and economic growth. Undoubtedly, this is because the industrial sector has been one of the early adopters of new or disruptive technologies (Khan *et al.*, 2021). In today's rapidly emerging landscape of high-performance computing, internet connectivity and data services, the demand for cutting-edge technological solutions in industrial settings in developing economies has never been more critical. This has led to the prevalent implementation of technologies such as Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data Analytics, Machine Learning (ML), Augmented/Virtual Reality (AR/VR), Energy Storage, Smart Automation, 3-D printing, and Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) which have proven to be robust triggers of performance in all sectors of the economy.

The adoption of technological innovation is crucial towards the realization of economic growth and development. Numerous industrial clusters have been created across the world, and considerable technological innovations and development have occurred in diverse sectors through these business formations (Akinwale *et al.*, 2017; Kim *et al.*, 2023). Based on the heterogeneity of industrial clusters, the synergetic collaborative agglomeration of firms into clusters to promote economic growth through technological innovation channels plays a critical role in improving technological innovation capabilities (Hao and Xiao, 2021).

The influence of industrial clusters can fast-track and transform to innovation-driven economic development models where the intensity of industrial firms to embrace and sustain technological innovation is high. However, industrial clusters have been identified as an important sector in developing economies, given their enormous impact on economic gains, exports and employment (Kongmanila and Takahashib, 2009; United Nations Industrial Development Organization, 2022). More so, in today's digitalized economy, industrial clusters are gradually providing an avenue for sustainable competitive advantage and economic development (Osarenkhoe and Fjellström, 2017).

Nevertheless, developing economies are constantly eager to leapfrog and deploy more advanced technological innovations through interconnectivity, automation, integration, simulation and real-time data usage, so as to enjoy full benefits from new or disruptive technologies, and also to cushion the effects of various economic and business challenges presently encountered in global value chains. In order for firms in Nigerian industrial settings to keep up with technological advancement and economic change around the world, the Government has introduced various initiatives over the decades via industrial clusters to surmount the challenges impeding development in the sector (Ugoani and Ibeenwo, 2015).

Notably, industrial clusters need to be continually strengthened through industrial technology and financial development to stimulate economic growth (Bank of Industry, 2018). Understanding this, the Nigerian

Table 1: Description of Internet-based Technological Innovations.

Internet-based technological innovations (IBTI)	Indicators
Communications and information systems management	IBTI1
Digital transformation	IBTI2
Interactive and virtual engagement applications	IBTI3
Database management and computing services	IBTI4
Cloud-based services	IBTI5
Production and processing	IBTI6
Fleet management (vehicle tracking)	IBTI7
Surveillance and monitoring (IT security systems)	IBTI8
Artificial intelligence	IBTI9
Global positioning system	IBTI10
Drones	IBTI11
Other IBTI	IBTI12

government recognizes that it would yield better impact to support and implement policy focused on promoting industrial firms that share common technological resources and co-locate. However, given the continuous upsurge in globalization, the Nigerian Government is keen and geared towards attaining and sustaining competitive advantage in the international market by initiating changes with the aim of strengthening and regulating industrial clusters, while promoting the sustainability of the industrial competitiveness (Bank of Industry, 2018).

Meanwhile, the successful application of Internet technology across the globe has had a substantial effect on technology adoption and usage behaviour in emerging economies (Zhang, 2018). Particularly, the application of the Internet has been acknowledged to be one of the most notable discoveries of the century as its adoption has greatly transformed economic and social segments of society (Roblek *et al.*, 2020). While its discovery was a remarkable feat for transformation across the world (Rao, 1999), the “Internet” as a driver of technological innovations has spread exponentially across industrial segments, and has been recognized as one of the most vital technologies in this century. As a matter of fact, it has brought about the emergence of the “Industry 4.0” and digital transformations in economies around the globe (Lee *et al.*, 2014).

Despite the swift pace of technological innovations in recent years, particularly in industrial arenas and infrastructural development, the opportunities and challenges connected with industrial clusters have become more complex overtime. This has led to more diverse paths of structural transformation leading to the pervasive and quickening pace of technological change and the globalization and fragmentation of production across the world (Naudé and Nagler, 2015). However, examining the determinants of adoption of IBTI are pertinent, notably at this point in time when the world is at the dawn of 4IR, and developing economies are eager to implement more advanced technological innovations, so as to derive the full benefits of industrial technological transformation.

The adoption of IBTI has helped industrial firms to be relevant and competitive globally (Olomu *et al.*, 2023), but

despite the current pace of global business transformation, there are few studies on how evolving technological innovations has impacted contemporary challenges and opportunities in the African business context. More so, there are assumptions that the determinants of technology policy and innovation are failing to create reliable economic gains and advancement to close technological disparities, especially in developing economies. The understanding of the determinants of IBTI will help stakeholders and policy-makers implement these systems more efficiently, thereby improving the speed of the advancement of Industry 4.0 towards the realization of the SDGs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Adoption and The Enabling Factors of Internet-Based Technological Innovations

Adoption refers to the application and deployment of a specific innovation. Similarly, according to Azam (2015), the adoption of a particular technology could mean the perceptual state of acceptance of the deployment of an innovation. Consequently, Internet-based technological innovations (as shown in Table 1) could be referred to as the operations, activities or services deployed with the use of communication infrastructure of the Internet or Internet-enabled devices (Olomu *et al.*, 2023). Firms in industrial clusters often engage in several activities and innovation strategies to ascertain the acquisition and implementation of technologies pivotal to innovation and sustainable development. These are however determined by various key factors and conditions.

Thus, the viewpoint about the adoption of IBTI necessitates an understanding at the systems level, so as to establish the strength of the determinants of the technological innovations and how they interrelate to lessen the uncertainties and phenomena connected to technological adoption strategies. This is majorly because the consideration for technological innovations has now shifted from a single firm’s perspective to the perception of clusters within which the firms are situated.

Furthermore, the study considers several theories and models in the literature to develop and validate the conceptual background for the determinants of the adoption of IBTI in the study. The theoretical model for the adoption of Internet-based technological innovations reflects factors that influence the inclination to adopt innovations within industrial clusters. Firstly, the literature establishes the technology-organization-environment (TOE) framework which categorized the determinants that is, technological factors, which can be internal or external to the firm (Baker, 2012) were considered in the study. TOE model has been widely used to investigate and examine several types and patterns of adoption of technological innovations. For instance, cloud-based services (Lal and Bharadwaj, 2020), social commerce (Abed, 2020), e-business (Oliveira and Martins, 2010; 2011), inter-organizational system standards (Chan and Chong, 2012), radio frequency identification (Wang *et al.*, 2010; Adhiarna *et al.*, 2013), health care information system (Yang *et al.*, 2013), cloud computing (Lian *et al.*, 2013) and customer management systems (Hung *et al.*, 2010). Consequently, the TOE model is found appropriate on theoretical grounds, as IBTI adoption decision may be subjected to attitudes toward using technology (technological factors) as well as features and credibility of the technology suppliers (the environmental factors) and the facilitating conditions (organizational factors).

Similarly, the theoretical framework further considers several competing models such as transaction cost economics (TCE) and the technology acceptance model (TAM). The TCE model presents the basis for recognizing costs as a driver of technology adoption. The theory is assumed as alternative approaches of negotiating transactions (governance structures such as firms, labour markets and regulators) that lessen transactional or resultant costs (Williamson, 1998). The TCE further speculates that a firm's structure is critical and attains economic proficiency by reducing the costs of business by all means and that each transaction attains coordination costs of controlling, monitoring and managing transactions and billings (Young, 2013). Therefore, TCE entails the costs and prices of running economic systems and technological functionalities of firms. As such, costs and value for money are primary determinants of a firm's decision to adopt a technological innovation, and as such, costs must be separated from production costs. Thus, economic flexibility (EFY) and price value (PV) are the constructs considered from the basis of transaction costs in economic models.

More so, the TAM has been extensively useful in technology adoption studies ranging from IT processes and management systems to web-based applications and enterprise systems (Hess *et al.*, 2014). The framework has also been useful in understanding the dynamics of adoption of technology at firm levels. More so, TAM is known to be valid, robust, detailed and central to learning firm-level usage of technology (Gangwar *et al.*, 2014), as it proposes

universal factors and supplies more significant insights into understanding firms' views about the deployment and implementation processes of particular systems. It is pertinent to note that the decision to adopt modern technology is commonly influenced by the need and understanding of the key entities involved in strategic decision processes such as chief executive officers and chief information officers as the case may be (Peansupap and Walker, 2006). Accordingly, two major variables and constructs which play crucial functions in the decision to accept or reject information technology in TAM are performance expectancy (perceived usefulness) and effort expectancy (perceived ease of use). They are found appropriate as usefulness and ease of use of technology could determine the decision of a firm to adopt Internet-based technological innovations.

Conceptual Framework and Hypotheses Development

The conceptual framework of the study was formulated based on the technology-organization-environment (TOE) model, technology adoption model (TAM) and transaction cost economics (TCE). These models were developed to identify measurements from the literature as described in Table 2. The theoretical basis of the TOE model, TAM and TCE considers seven measurements namely: attitudes toward using technology (ATUT), facilitating conditions (FC), service provider's credibility (SPC), performance expectancy (PE), effort expectancy (EE), economic flexibility (EFY) and price value (PV) were identified for the factors determining the adoption of IBTI.

Within the comprehensive evolutionary viewpoints, the study's statistical models are constructed to incorporate the tendencies and agglomeration patterns of arrays of the economic, technological, environmental, organizational and socio-cultural determinants, in conjunction with innovation activities, focusing on connections among the factors in the adoption of different types of IBTI. The following explains each of the hypotheses formulated in the study.

Attitudes toward using technology (ATUT)

ATUT is established on the TOE model and postulated by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975), who characterized attitude as an individual's sentiment or understanding about accomplishing the desired behaviour. For this study, the construct ATUT means the feeling regarding the adoption of IBTI by firms in industrial clusters. The awareness and responsiveness of the management as regarding the adoption of new technologies and their collective attitude to experiment (Lian *et al.*, 2013; Alshamaila *et al.*, 2013), and the readiness and attitude to commit resources on the technologies (Low *et al.*, 2011; Chan and Chong, 2012) are regarded significant variables to evaluate top management regarding IBTI adoption. The industrial cluster firm's management awareness, decision to support, ascertain value for money, and willingness to take risk with novel ideas and

Table 2: Description of the Model Constructs for Adoption of the IBTI.

Constructs	Indicators	Measurements	References
Attitudes toward using technology	ATUT1	Our management is fully aware of the economic gains that can be attained from the adoption of IBTI.	Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975; Low <i>et al.</i> , 2011; Chan and Chong, 2012; Lian <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Alshamaila <i>et al.</i> , 2013.
	ATUT2	Our management understands and supports the adoption of IBTI.	
	ATUT3	Our management is willing to invest on Internet-based technologies.	
	ATUT4	Our management understand that the adoption of IBTI ascertain value for money.	
	ATUT5	Our management is prepared to take the risk with innovative technologies and ideas.	
Performance expectancy	PE1	We find Internet-based technological innovations useful in our company's daily life and activities.	Venkatesh <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Oliveira <i>et al.</i> , 2016.
	PE2	Using IBTI increase our company's chances of realizing things that are crucial to us.	
	PE3	Using IBTI helps our company to achieving things more quickly.	
	PE4	Using IBTI increases our company's productivity.	
	PE5	Using IBTI makes our company's work much easier.	
Effort expectancy	EE1	Learning ways to use Internet-based technological innovations more effectively is easy for our company.	Venkatesh <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Lal and Bharadwaj, 2020.
	EE2	Our company's interactions with IBTI are clear and understandable.	
	EE3	Our company finds IBTI easy to use.	
	EE4	It is easy for our company's staff to become skillful at using IBTI.	
Service provider's credibility	SPC1	Our Internet service providers are experts in what they do.	Chan and Chong, 2012; Alshamaila <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Lee <i>et al.</i> , 2014.
	SPC2	Our Internet service providers possess good amount of technical experience.	
	SPC3	Our Internet service providers are reliable in terms of providing efficient services.	
	SPC4	Our Internet service providers are trust-worthy.	
	SPC5	Our Internet service provider's brand is popularly known.	
	SPC6	Our Internet service providers are able to anticipate and quickly respond to our need.	
	SPC7	Our Internet service providers are able to quickly understand and adjust to our company's specific needs.	
	SPC8	Our Internet service providers are capable of dealing with market uncertainty associated to technological changes.	
Economic flexibility	EFY1	The cost of Internet varies and based on usage level.	Williamson, 1998; Young, 2013; Lal and Bharadwaj, 2020.
	EFY2	Internet service providers give flexible or adjustable pricing preferences based on access to the technological functionalities.	
	EFY3	The pricing structure of IBTI services is transparent and metered.	
	EFY4	The investment on Internet-based technological innovations have become a variable or adjustable expenditure on weekly/ monthly/ yearly basis.	
	EFY5	It is easy to switch methods of payment for using Internet-based technology services in relation to traditional IT services.	
Facilitating conditions	FC1	Our company has the required resources to adequately adopt Internet-based technological innovations.	Venkatesh <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Oliveira <i>et al.</i> , 2016.
	FC2	Our company has the required knowledge and expertise to use IBTI.	
	FC3	IBTI are compatible or well-matched with other technologies we use.	
	FC4	Our company can get assistance from other firms when we have issues using IBTI.	
Price value	PV1	Internet-based technological innovations are reasonably priced.	Venkatesh <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Oliveira <i>et al.</i> , 2016.
	PV2	IBTI are good value for the money to our company.	
	PV3	IBTI provide good value to our company at the current price.	

benefit from the adoption are described in Table 2 and theorized as:

H1: Attitudes toward using technology positively influences the adoption of Internet-based technological innovations.

Facilitating conditions (FC)

FC is theorized on the TOE model and established in UTAUT and UTAUT2. It is characterized by the firms' understanding of the support system and infrastructure available to easily adopt new technologies (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2012). Hence, FC means the rate at which the industrial firms perceive that IBTI adoption can be maintained and managed by current organizational technical infrastructure and resources. Staff of firms in the industrial clusters may not be fully aware of the technical features and usefulness of IBTI, but the availability of more support systems, commitment and solutions can further facilitate their usage efforts to adopt IBTI. Thus, firm's IBTI adoption and usage is linked to support and infrastructural solutions and resources available to them. However, firms' employees are heterogeneous as related to their individual innovativeness to new technologies, as more innovative ones are most likely to adopt the innovations. The firm's technical infrastructure, expertise, compatibility of IBTI with other technologies and accessibility to technical support in the adoption of IBTI are described in Table 2 and is hypothesized as:

H2: Facilitating conditions positively influence the adoption of Internet-based technological innovations.

Service provider's credibility (SPC)

SPC is established on the TOE model and it is used in the study to explain the decisions by the firms in the industrial clusters on the believability and reliability of the Internet and IT solution providers. For any new technology, SPC is dependent on the availability of IT experts, implementation and provision of IT services past (Lee *et al.*, 2013) and the quality of IT expertise, as the frequent changes in the IT world usually necessitates that service providers must always be at the top of their game in order to remain relevant. In addition, SPC depends greatly on swift responses to market needs and uncertainties (Alshamaila *et al.*, 2013) and also rapid anticipation to new technological transformation in dynamic business environments by the service providers. The level of trustworthiness, credibility (Chan and Chong, 2012), and brand image or reputation (Lee *et al.*, 2013) of the IT service provider is crucial as data privacy and security are of great essence to firms. Also, the availability of IT service are critical to the firm's choice of service provider in making the adoption decision. The ease of adaptability to firm's specific needs, efficient service delivery and competency in dealing with business uncertainty related to technological dynamics are important to industrial firms, and all these forms are described in Table 2 and hypothesized that:

H3: Service provider's credibility positively influences the adoption of Internet-based technological innovations.

Performance expectancy (PE)

PE is also known as perceived usefulness and it is supported by the TAM theory (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2012). It is referred to as the rate at which firms in industrial clusters believe

that deploying IBTI will help them achieve their objectives, and realize benefits in job performance in selling and marketing their products to the consumers. Therefore, if firms anticipate to enjoy more benefits from the adoption of IBTI in getting more prospective customers and selling more goods, they are most likely to develop a stronger intention to adopt the technology. The firms would be eager to adopt IBTI if they anticipate business growth and performance potentials in the technology. Research has shown that firms that implemented information systems have enjoyed benefits (Oliveira *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, firm's adoption of Internet-based technological innovations would increase if they perceive more benefits from doing so, as described in Table 2 and theorized as:

H4: Performance expectancy positively influences the adoption of Internet-based technological innovations.

Effort expectancy (EE)

EE also known as perceived ease of use is fully established and supported by the TAM theory (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2012). It is positively linked with the perceived ease of use perspective in TAM (Migliore, 2022). EE is ultimately considered important at the firm level as decision to adopt a technological innovation is mostly influenced by IT/ ICT heads (Lal and Bharadwaj, 2020). However, in this study, EE is characterized as the rate of ease connected to firms' adoption of Internet-based technological innovations. Firms in industrial clusters would hesitate to deploy a technological innovation if they do not feel assured or motivated to do so. As such, if the firms observe that the technological innovations are easy to adopt, they are more likely to give it a try. Also, if industrial firms feel that efforts needed to adopt IBTI is highly demanding, they might feel discouraged, and deterred from using such technology, while they remain with their traditional ways of carrying out their job functions. Thus, firms adopt IBTI if they feel at ease to do so. This is described in Table 2 and hypothesized as:

H5: Effort expectancy positively influences the adoption of Internet-based technological innovations.

Economic flexibility (EFY)

EFY is fully supported by the TCE theory, and it means that firm incur a transactional cost when it discovers that engaging and maintaining IT solutions within is much costlier than if outsourced (Lal and Bharadwaj, 2020). As such, IBTI allows transparency and flexibility in terms of available payment options to firms in industrial clusters centred on the access to functionality and usage as the case may be. Also, firms can choose any method of payment depending on the requirements, usage and functionality with subscriptions or variable spending on weekly/monthly/yearly basis. However, firms get flexibility as regards switching payment methods based on their requirements. Furthermore, Internet resources and solutions usage are monitored, metered and controlled, providing adequate and

timely reports to the firms by the Internet service provider regarding the status of billings. This gives firms flexibility in handling their expenses on IT on a weekly/monthly/yearly basis. EFY are described in Table 2 and then theorized in the study as:

H6: Economic flexibility positively influences the adoption of Internet-based technological innovations.

Price value (PV)

PV is fully supported by the TCE theory and also by UTAUT2 to mean cognitive interchange among the perceived benefits of the technological innovations and the monetary cost of deployment (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2012). It entails the monetary cost of the adoption of IBTI as the pricing and cost structures may have a substantial effect on use of technology. As such, the pricing and cost structure is conceptualised along with the value of products to decide the perceived worth of products. However, it is good when the gains of deploying a technology are understood to be higher than the cost, as such price value has a positive and impactful gain on adoption. Also, adoption improves as the gains on technology are more and the cost is low. Therefore, price value is a determinant of adoption of technological innovations as it portrays reasonably priced and worthy value for money at the existing price. Thus, described in Table 2 and theorized as:

H7: Price value positively influences the adoption of Internet-based technological innovations.

METHODOLOGY, ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Data

The data used for this study was from a survey carried out in the year 2022. The survey focused only the fast-moving consumer goods (FCMG) firms located in industrial clusters that had at least fifty (50) employees and based in the Southwestern region of Nigeria. The choice of the region was influenced by the prevalence of industrial clusters and proximity to infrastructure for communications network facilities.

Similarly, these firms have access to knowledge support system, learning and technological infrastructure in the clusters. With the sample determination method established by Cochran (1977), a multi-stage sampling technique was deployed to select a total number of 384 industrial clusters' firms belonging to the International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities (ISIC) Rev.4 code 10–33, out of which 89.3% (343) response rate were completed, recovered and found appropriate for statistical analysis.

Methodology

The study considered both descriptive and inferential statistics for the analyses. Frequencies and percentages were

the descriptive statistics used in the study to describe the overall perception or observation of the variables tested, while correlation, regression, and confirmatory and exploratory factor analyses were applied to examine the relationships among the constructs. The instrument found appropriate for the analysis was the partial least square (PLS) with statistical technique based on structural equation modelling using SmartPLS version 4 (Ringle *et al.*, 2022). Structural equation modelling entails evaluating the fit and validity of the model, and it requires assessing the fit of the measurement model by analyzing the hypothesized relationships among the latent constructs.

In order to determine when the firms fully implemented the IBTI, the length of the adoption was evaluated using the number of years they started deploying the technological innovations officially up to the data collection date (Table 3). However, to ascertain the factors determining the adoption of the IBTI in the last five (5) years of operations, the responses of the industrial clusters' firms were measured by the categories of the determinants with varying constructs. Table 2 provides a list of determinants of the adoption of IBTI which all the industrial firms were expected to respond to in the questionnaire.

Similarly, the industrial firms were asked to indicate the degree to which they considered each factor in the adoption of IBTI in the last five (5) years using ordinal scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" (scale 1) to "Strongly agree" (scale 5). The study was purposely limited to the last five (5) years of industrial firms' operations in the clusters, given that the full implementation of Internet-based information systems and innovation activities formally became more profound and decisive in most emerging economies with that period, notably in sub-Saharan Africa within the period (Olomu *et al.*, 2023).

Analyses and results

Of the 343 industrial firms in the sample, higher percentage of the firms had adopted IBTI over the last three (3) years in their operations, and a large number have deployed the technological innovations in day-to-day economic, business and core activities (Table 3). Nonetheless, despite the rising impact of IBTI in the industrial setting around the world, majority of the firms only started using the technologies lately. This is an indication that the firms in industrial clusters in Nigeria are late majority adopters of IBTI. These firms are mostly characterized for the adoption of new technologies when there is no other alternative available and no option to change is undeniable (Olomu *et al.*, 2023).

Validity and reliability analyses for the factors determining the adoption of IBTI

In order to validate the suitability of the measurement scales, the convergent validity was examined. The composite reliability (CR) coefficient statistically must be higher than 0.7 for the appropriate construct and ascertained that the indicators suitably express the latent

variable. The average variance extracted (AVE) for all the constructs was more than 0.5 to validate the convergent validity. As revealed in Table 4, the AVE indicates that the latent variable explains more than half of the variance of its indicators (Hair *et al.*, 2017). More so, the degree of associations among the latent factors show that each item was statistically significant (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

Table 3: Period of the Adoption of Internet tTechnological Innovations in the Industrial Clusters.

Firms' characteristics	Length of the IBTI adoption	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
< 1 year	2	0.6
1-2 years	54	15.7
2-3 years	49	14.3
3-4 years	123	35.9
> 4 years	115	33.5

Structural model and regression analysis for the factors determining the adoption of IBTI

The structural model tested the relationship between the exogenous factors and the endogenous variable (IBTI adoption). Q^2 value was attained by the blindfolding process to ascertain cross-validated redundancy measurement for endogenous construct used to measure the predictive relevance of the model. Also, f^2 was used to determine the extent to which the endogenous construct supported the R^2 value. Furthermore, as depicted in Table 6, Q^2 value is larger than zero which demonstrates that the model has predictive significance (0.643), i.e., IBTI had suitable predictive relevance. In effect sizes (f^2), values of 0.02–0.15, 0.15–0.35, and ≥ 0.35 stipulate that an exogenous latent variable represents a small, medium, or large effect correspondingly. Thus, SPC, FC, EFY and PV had small impact on adoption of IBTI, while ATUT, PE and EE had

Figure 1: Structural Model for the Determinants of the Adoption of IBTI in the Nigerian Industrial Clusters.

Furthermore, the standardized measurement of the instruments and scales confirmed internal consistency by inter-item uniformity measures of Cronbach's coefficient. Hence, the Cronbach's alpha coefficients from 0.735 to 0.937 recommended that the scales used were acceptable in clarifying the appropriate latent variables. Also, the factors that provided least to the explanatory power of the model were disregarded. In total, six items were eliminated for low latency as the values were significantly unrelated, and the loadings within latent and observed variables were more in all cases (IBTI9, SPC2, SPC3, SPC6, PE3, and EFY2). Therefore, it can be deduced that the latent variables suitably explained the observed variables.

Fornell-Larcker criterion (under the main diagonal) and Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) (above the main diagonal). The diagonal elements (in bold) are the square roots of the average variance extracted (variance shared between constructs and measures).

a medium impact on adoption of IBTI.

The result of the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) ratio as postulated by Henseler *et al.* (2015) was used to determine the difference among the observed and the predicted correlation, thereby indicating the fitness of the model. Hence, the coefficient below 0.08 is understood to be suitable. The study's model derived an appropriate coefficient close to the threshold (SRMR = 0.04). Therefore, the fitness of the hypothesized model was discovered to be suitable, and outcome of the overall structural model with the hypothesized associations (Table 6). Subsequently, the parameter estimates showed that t-values were higher than 1.96.

The results revealed that the connections of the adoption of IBTI with the PE (H4) ($\beta = 0.392$; $p < 0.05$), EE (H5) ($\beta = 0.607$; $p < 0.05$) and PV (H7) ($\beta = 0.266$; $p < 0.05$) were positive and relevant, therefore the stated hypotheses were accepted. Similarly, the relationship of IBTI with the ATUT (H1) ($\beta = -0.109$; $p < 0.05$), SPC (H2) ($\beta = -0.039$; $p < 0.05$), FC (H3) ($\beta = -0.106$; $p < 0.05$) and EFY (H6) ($\beta = -0.078$; $p < 0.05$) were negative, but significantly

impact the adoption of IBTI, thus the hypotheses were also accepted. The model explains 95.1% of the adoption of IBTI, signifying a good explanatory power.

power, demonstrating 95.1% of the variation in the adoption of IBTI in the selected industrial clusters. The study further revealed that EE is the most decisive

Table 4: Reliability of Items and Constructs for the Factors Determining the Adoption of IBTI.

Construct	Indicators	Loadings	AVE	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability
IBTI	IBTI1	0.791	0.620	0.937	0.942
	IBTI2	0.688			
	IBTI3	0.676			
	IBTI4	0.911			
	IBTI5	0.765			
	IBTI6	0.780			
	IBTI7	0.924			
	IBTI8	0.845			
	IBTI10	0.859			
	IBTI11	0.673			
	IBTI12	0.693			
	ATUT	ATUT1			
ATUT2		0.758			
ATUT3		0.807			
ATUT4		0.859			
ATUT5		0.829			
SPC	SPC1	0.922	0.511	0.825	0.873
	SPC4	0.634			
	SPC5	0.609			
	SPC7	0.721			
	SPC8	0.643			
FC	FC1	0.874	0.677	0.840	0.882
	FC2	0.817			
	FC3	0.897			
	FC4	0.676			
PE	PE1	0.771	0.603	0.778	0.784
	PE2	0.841			
	PE4	0.793			
	PE5	0.694			
EE	EE 1	0.883	0.675	0.837	0.844
	EE 2	0.836			
	EE 3	0.856			
	EE 4	0.701			
EFY	EFY1	0.872	0.763	0.896	0.898
	EFY3	0.903			
	EFY4	0.919			
	EFY5	0.795			
PV	PV1	0.889	0.660	0.735	0.739
	PV2	0.822			
	PV3	0.704			

Table 5: Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion and Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio).

	IBTI	ATUT	SPC	FC	PE	EE	EFY	PV	VIF
IBTI	0.873	0.720	0.681	0.555	0.406	0.776	0.287	0.420	–
ATUT	0.416	0.856	0.755	0.563	0.534	0.464	0.279	0.531	2.40
SPC	0.411	0.411	0.893	0.705	0.729	0.560	0.415	0.018	2.10
FC	0.689	0.189	0.210	0.890	0.432	0.764	0.611	0.448	2.80
PE	0.750	0.450	0.370	0.497	0.869	0.655	0.392	0.076	2.74
EE	0.526	0.716	0.463	0.524	0.733	0.899	0.056	0.678	2.53
EFY	0.650	0.650	0.459	0.555	0.523	0.577	0.887	0.414	2.15
PV	0.622	0.622	0.518	0.654	0.421	0.278	0.476	0.869	1.44

The proposed theoretical model identified all the variables as significant determinants of adoption of IBTI. This is an indication that the model has good and sound explanatory

determinant influencing the adoption of IBTI. This result corroborated with preceding studies such as Oliveira *et al.* (2016) and Chopdar and Sivakumar (2019). This outcome

suits the divergent adoption patterns among firms in the industrial clusters, as late adopters are known to be less price sensitive than early adopters (Frank *et al.*, 2015). However, the Nigerian firms failed to evaluate the relevance of adoption of IBTI in terms of monetary costs and benefits, possibly as a result of the low level of adoption of the technological innovations (Olomu *et al.*, 2023).

In addition, the facilitating conditions as determinant in the adoption of IBTI among the firms in the industrial clusters considered in the study showed that the firms keenly recognized the useful and advanced utilities of innovations, but are impeded by inadequate enabling conditions to adopt the new technologies more successfully. The firms' attitudes toward using technology critically led to low level of investment on facilitating infrastructure that could aid proper adoption, while unavailability of adequate economic

conditions to successfully adopt emerging and disruptive technologies. Notably, the firms' attitudes toward using technology critically led to low level of investment on facilitating infrastructure that could aid proper adoption, while unavailability of adequate economic flexibility of the innovations provided by the service providers also discouraged the firms from effective adoption of IBTI in the clusters.

The study explains how to adequately and efficiently utilize available technological capabilities and tailor policy towards explicit needs, thereby prioritizing economic, technological, organizational and societal needs and opportunities for sustainable development. Furthermore, the study ascertains that interactions and collaborations within the industrial clusters would subject the firms to take decisions that are imperative and conducive to innovation and creativity.

Table 6: Results of the Structural Model for the Factors Determining the Adoption of IBTI.

Coefficient	Path Coefficient	t-value	p-value	Decision	f ²	Q ²	R ²	SRMR
H1 ATUT → IBTI	-0.109	3.892	0.000	Accepted	0.027			
H2 SPC → IBTI	-0.039	5.196	0.005	Accepted	0.014			
H3 FC → IBTI	-0.106	3.314	0.033	Accepted	0.117			
H4 PE → IBTI	0.392	2.325	0.049	Accepted	0.262			
H5 EE → IBTI	0.607	2.082	0.037	Accepted	0.226			
H6 EFY → IBTI	-0.078	2.387	0.017	Accepted	0.005			
H7 PV → IBTI	0.266	4.320	0.038	Accepted	0.139			
						0.643	0.951	0.04

Level of significant of p < 0.05

flexibility of the innovations provided by the service providers also discouraged the industrial firms from effective adoption. Furthermore, the results show that TAM has a stronger explanatory power on IBTI adoption when matched with the TOE and TCE. Also, the results demonstrate that TOE, TAM and TCE are appropriate for analyzing the existing determinants influencing the adoption of IBTI in many contexts. This conclusion is one of the major contributions to the existing literature.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Conclusion

The study delivers a theoretical value by examining how specific factors predict the adoption of IBTI within industrial clusters to determine technological and economic gains, especially in developing economies where firms in those industrial clusters are curious and eager to leapfrog to economic transformations. The findings revealed that there are strong interactions among the dimensions of the model for the determinants of adoption of IBTI.

However, the facilitating conditions as drivers in the adoption of IBTI in the industrial clusters indicate that the firms recognized the useful and advanced utilities of innovations, but are impeded by inadequate enabling

Also, the study contributes immensely to the literature on issues relating to the adoption phenomena of technological innovations and development of latecomer industrial settings. This is critical as the nature and strength of business environments in the both developed and emerging economies for growth and structural transformations demand decisive connections among new technologies, learning, knowledge support systems, sectors, firms, industrial clusters, labour and foreign markets, regulators and Government. Similarly, the findings are additions to the literature based on the peculiar nature of the economic, technological, environmental, organizational and social-cultural factors of developing economies, in particular, the African countries.

Policy implications

This study provides economic and managerial implications and contributions for Nigerian industrial clusters. Adoption of Internet-based technological systems to drive economic growth and technological change is vital, but the decision process leading to implementation of the innovations is more expedient. Furthermore, the study shows that proper assessment of needs and opportunities of technological innovations would help in reforming current business practices, by producing and enhancing business and sectoral productivity, and using the innovations to stimulate new production functions.

Holistically, the study reveals that the understanding of the determinants of IBTI would help policy-makers and stakeholders implement information systems more efficiently, improve the speed of the advancement of Industry 4.0. and attaining the SDGs. Since public policy and actions play a vital role in driving the technological and economic factors, promoting accelerated adoption of new technologies through policy mechanisms is pertinent at refocusing and localizing supply chains and strengthening indigenous technological capabilities at various levels in Nigeria.

This is an indication that the industry can leapfrog and deploy advanced technological innovations with proper policy formulation and integration of technological capabilities and resources, which is critical for global competitiveness and technological infrastructural development. More importantly, the availability of technological infrastructure is critical to support the performance of industrial firms, which would improve their ability to compete in international markets through the acquisition and application of the new technologies. However, there is a need to intensify greater infrastructural and knowledge support systems to fully obtain benefits from new technologies and grow learning capabilities to promote industrial and economic development at large.

However, underdevelopment and persistent low level of industrialization still loom in major areas of developing economies, but improving the capacity to utilize the timing of technological and economic cycles effectively is most critical in latecomer settings by understanding the impact of agglomeration patterns and dynamics.

REFERENCES

- Abed, Salma S. (2020). Social commerce adoption using TOE framework: An empirical investigation of Saudi Arabian SMEs. *International Journal of Information Management*, 53, 102-118.
- Adhiarna, N., Min Hwang, Y., Park, M. J., Rho, J. J. (2013). An integrated framework for RFID adoption and diffusion with a stage-scale-scope cubicle model: A case of Indonesia, *International Journal of Information Management*, 33(2), 378-389, ISSN 0268-4012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2012.10.001>
- Akinwale, Y.O., Adepoju, A.O., and Olomu, M.O. (2017). The impact of technological innovation on SME's profitability in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research, Innovation and Commercialization*, 1(1), 74-92.
- Alshamaila, Y., Papagiannidis, S., and Li, F. (2013). Cloud computing adoption by SMEs in the north east of England: A multi-perspective framework. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 26(3), 250-275. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17410391311325225>
- Azam, M. (2015). Diffusion of ICT and SME Performance, E-Services Adoption: Processes by Firms in Developing Nations. *Advances in Business Marketing and Purchasing*, 23A, 7-290. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1069-096420150000023005>
- Baker, J. (2012). The Technology-Organization-Environment Framework. In: Dwivedi, Y.K., Scott, L.M., Schneberger, L. and Systems, I.S., Eds., *Information Systems Theory: Explaining and Predicting Our Digital Society*, University of Hamburg, Hamburg, 232-243. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-6108-2_12
- Bank of Industry (2018). *Industrial Clusters and Economic Development in Nigeria*. Working Paper Series, No. 4, 27th November. Available at: <https://www.boi.ng/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/BOI-Working-Paper-Series-No4-Industry-Clusters-and-Economic-Development.pdf>
- Chan, F.T.S., and Chong, A.Y.L. (2012). A SEM-Neural Network Approach for Understanding Determinants of Interorganizational System Standard Adoption and Performances. *Decision Support Systems*, 54, 621-630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2012.08.009>
- Chopdar, P. K., and Sivakumar, V. J. (2019). Understanding continuance usage of mobile shopping applications in India: the role of espoused cultural values and perceived risk. *Behaviour and Information Technology*, 38(1), 42-64.
- Cochran, W.G. (1977). *Sampling techniques*, 3rd edition, John Wiley and Sons, New York.
- Fishbein, M., and Ajzen, I. (1975). Belief, Attitude, Intention and Behaviour: An Introduction to Theory and Research. Addison-Wesley, Boston, MA.
- Fornell, C., and Larcker, D. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39-50. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3151312>
- Frank, B., Enkawa, T., Schvaneveldt, S. J., and Torrico, B. H. (2015). Antecedents and consequences of innate willingness to pay for innovations: Understanding motivations and consumer preferences of prospective early adopters. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 99, 252-266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2015.06.029>
- Gangwar, H., Date, H., and Raoot, A. (2014). Review on IT adoption: Insights from recent technologies. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 27, 488-502. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/JEIM-08-2012-0047>
- Hair, J.F., Hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C.M., and Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. 2nd Edition, Sage Publications Inc., Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Hair, J.F., Risher, J.J., Sarstedt, M., and Ringle, C.M. (2019). When to Use and How to Report the Results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31, 2-24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>
- Hao, J. and Xiao, L. (2021). Industrial co-agglomeration, technological innovation and economic growth: based on the mediating effect model. *Science & Technology Progress and Policy*, 38(11), 46-53. DOI: 10.6049/kjbydc.2020120434
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C.M., and Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the*

- Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8>
- Hung, M.-L., Chou, C., Chen, C.-H., and Own, Z.-Y. (2010). Learner readiness for online learning: Scale development and student perceptions. *Computers and Education*, 55(3), 1080–1090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2010.05.004>
- Khan, I. S., Ahmad, M. O., & Majava, J. (2021). Industry 4.0 and sustainable development: A systematic mapping of triple bottom line, Circular Economy and Sustainable Business Models perspectives. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126655>
- Kim, H., Hwang, S.-H., and Yoon, W. (2023). Industrial cluster, organization diversity, and innovation. *International Journal of Innovation Studies* 7, 187-195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijis.2023.03.002>
- Kongmanila, X., and Takahashib, Y. (2009). Inter-Firm Cooperation and Firm Performance: An Empirical Study of the Lao Garment Industrial Cluster. *Int. Journal of Business and Management*, 4(5), 3-17.
- Lal, P., and Bharadwaj, S.S. (2020). Understanding the drivers of Cloud-Based Service adoption and their impact on the organizational performance: An Indian perspective. *Journal of Global Information Management*, Vol. 28(1), 56-85.
- Lee, H-J., Jeong, Cho H., Xu, W., and Fairhurst, A. (2014). The influence of consumer traits and demographics on intention to use retail self-service checkouts. *Mark Intell Plan*, 28, 46–58.
- Lian, J-W., Yen, D. C., and Wang, Y-T. (2013). An exploratory study to understand the critical factors affecting the decision to adopt cloud computing in Taiwan hospital. *International Journal of Information Management*, 34(1), 28-36, ISSN 0268-4012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2013.09.004>
- Low, C., Chen, Y., and Wu, M. (2011). Understanding the determinants of cloud computing adoption. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 11(1), 1006-1023.
- Naudé, Wim., and Nagler, Paula (2015). Industrialization, Innovation Inclusion, UNIDO Inclusive and Sustainable Development Working Paper Series, Research, Statistics and Industrial Policy Branch WP 15, October 30.
- Oliveira, T., and Martins, M.F. (2011). Literature Review of Information Technology Adoption Models at Firm Level. *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems Evaluation*, 14(1), 110-121.
- Oliveira, T., Thomas, M., Baptista, G., and Campos, F. (2016). Mobile payment: Understanding the determinants of customer adoption and intention to recommend the technology. *Computers in Human Behaviour*, 61, 404-414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.03.030>
- Olomu, M. O., Binuyo, G. O., and Oyeibisi, T. O. (2023). The adoption and impact of Internet-based technological innovation on the performance of the industrial cluster firms. *Journal of Economy and Technology*. Volume 1, 164-178, ISSN 2949-9488. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ject.2023.11.004>
- Osarenkhoe, A., and Fjellström, D. (2017). Clusters' Vital Role in Promoting International Competitive Advantage - Towards an Explanatory Model of Regional Growth. *Journal of Regional Research*, 39, 175-194.
- Peansupap, V., and Walker, D.H.T. (2006). Innovation diffusion at the implementation stage of a construction project: a case study of information communication technology. *Construction Management and Economics*, 24(3), 321-332.
- Porter, M.E. (2008). Clusters, Innovation, and Competitiveness: New Findings and Implications for Policy. Slide presentation, Available at: http://www.isc.hbs.edu/pdf/20080122_EuropeanClusterPolicy.pdf
- Rao, B. (1999). The Internet and the revolution in the distribution: a cross-industry examination. *Technology in Society*, 21, 287-306.
- Ringle, C.M., Wende, S., and Becker, J.M. (2022). *SmartPLS 4*. Oststeinbek: SmartPLS GmbH, <http://www.smartpls.com>
- Roblek Vasja, Meško, M., Bach, M. P., Thorpe, O., and Šprajc, P. (2020). The Interaction between Internet, Sustainable Development, and Emergence of Society 5.0. *Data*, 5, 80. <https://doi.org/10.3390/data5030080>
- Ugoani, John N.N., and Ibeenwo, Grace I., (2015). Entrepreneurship Development and Employment Generation in Nigeria: A study of the National Directorate of Employment. *Independent Journal of Management and Production*, Vol. 6, No. 3, July-September, 687-710.
- United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) (2022). Advancing economic competitiveness and supporting small and medium industry clusters. Available at: <https://www.unido.org/our-focus/advancing-economic-competitiveness/supporting-small-and-medium-industry-clusters>
- Venkatesh, V., Thong JY., and Xu, X. (2012). Consumer acceptance and use of information technology: extending the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 36(1), 157-178.
- Wang, Y., Wang, Y., and Yang, Y. (2010). Understanding the Determinants of RFID Adoption in the Manufacturing Industry. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 77, 803-815. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2010.03.006>
- Williamson, O.E. (1998). Transaction Cost Economics: How It Works; Where It is Headed. *De Economist*, 146, 23–58. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1003263908567>
- Yang, Z., Kankanhalli, A., Ng, B. Y., and Lim, J. T. Y. (2013). Analyzing the enabling factors for the organizational decision to adopt healthcare information systems. *Decision Support Systems*, 55(3), 764-776.
- Young, S. (2013). Transaction Cost Economics. In: Idowu, S.O., Capaldi, N., Zu, L., Gupta, A.D. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Corporate Social Responsibility*.

Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-28036-8_221

Zhang, X. (2018). Frugal Innovation and the Digital Divide: Developing an extended model of the diffusion of innovations. *International Journal of Innovation Studies*, 2, 53-64.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijis.2018.06.001>